

Experimental Campaign and Numerical Validation of Isothermal Sloshing: Progress Toward the Implementation of Hydrogen Tanks in Civil Aviation

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The use of hydrogen as a fuel in the civil aviation industry represents one of the key technological challenges currently facing our society. In this context, the HASTA project seeks to contribute to the development of the technologies surrounding one of the fundamental components for the implementation of cryogenic hydrogen in aircraft: the fuel tank. Understanding the thermo-fluid-dynamic phenomena that occur inside a cryogenic tank is the primary objective of the HASTA project. Unlike other fields, the dynamic behavior of aircraft leads to the emergence of complex sloshing phenomena and heat and mass transfer processes between the different phases of hydrogen and/or the tank walls.

This knowledge spans three clearly defined areas: firstly, experimental evidence of these phenomena using scaled tanks and various working fluids; secondly, the development of numerical tools capable of accurately capturing the physical processes occurring within and across the tank boundaries; and finally, the development of reduced-order models (ROMs) capable of acting as a digital twin of the tank itself.

This work will focus on the first two aspects: experimental testing and numerical computation, both of which are being developed by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid as an active member of the project consortium. Given the importance of identifying sloshing regimes and their dependence on excitation conditions, particularly in future non-isothermal studies, this work focuses on the experiments and simulations conducted under isothermal conditions.

On the experimental side, we present the test campaign to be carried out with the new SHAKEIT sloshing facility. This setup aims to reproduce the typical motion profiles experienced by an aircraft from takeoff to landing, and to evaluate how these isothermal movements affect the sloshing behavior within the tank. Tests will include roll, surge, heave, and sway excitations, conducted at 1:15 scale tanks. These tests will yield both the fluid dynamic forces exerted on the tank and visual records of the fluid motion, captured via two mutually perpendicular cameras. Our intention is to carry out two complete experimental campaigns using two differently scaled tanks in order to assess whether scaling laws are able to accurately predict the behavior transition between the two, thereby enabling straightforward extrapolation to full scale. These experiments not only allow for scale-effect analysis but also serve as a valuable dataset for validating numerical methods and training reduced-order models.

Regarding the numerical approach, two independent methodologies will be presented. The first is a classical finite volume method in which the free surface is tracked using the Volume of Fluid (VOF) technique. The second is a meshless method based on Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH). The goal is for both methods to closely replicate the experimental results. In an isothermal sloshing context, where the fluid properties remain constant, the problem is primarily governed by two degrees of freedom: the kinematic motion profile and the tank filling level. A comparative analysis between numerical and experimental results, both in terms of fluid forces acting on the tank and the resulting sloshing regimes will be presented as part of this study.

In conclusion, this work aims to develop an experimental campaign that serves as a foundation for the validation of the numerical tools developed, constituting a key milestone in the advancement of the HASTA project.

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